

**FEATURES OF THE CONCEPT OF MORAL IMPROVEMENT OF
PERSONALITY OF CENTRAL ASIA THINKERS****Pulatova Dildor Akmalovna****PhD, Professor****Alphaganus University, Uzbekistan**

Abstract: In the dawn of the 21st century, humanity finds itself at a crossroads, grappling with unprecedented global challenges that stem from a profound disconnection between cultural advancements and moral foundations. This period of human history is marked by remarkable scientific and technological progress, yet it is also characterized by a deepening crisis of values, driven by materialism and a pragmatic approach to life's meaning. This crisis has prompted a reevaluation of the developmental paradigms of Western civilization, questioning its ideological orientations and ideals. Amidst this existential search for direction, there is a turning to the traditional teachings of Eastern philosophy, particularly those from Central Asia, for guidance. These teachings, with their emphasis on spirituality, moral values, and the pursuit of perfection ("kamal"), offer a counterpoint to the prevailing ethos of technogenic development. Central Asian thinkers such as Farabi, Ibn Sina, Biruni, and Alisher Navoi, with their focus on the moral law of Zoroastrianism and the continuous struggle between virtue and vice, present a vision of human perfection that integrates knowledge, wisdom, and moral action. Their works, advocating for a harmonious relationship between the individual and society, underscore the importance of moral improvement, the integrity of the world, and the universal harmony achievable through virtuous deeds and wisdom. This abstract highlights the relevance of these traditional teachings in addressing the contemporary moral dilemmas faced by humanity and suggests a pathway towards a more spiritually aligned and morally grounded civilization.

Keywords: Moral and cultural disconnection, materialism and pragmatism, western civilization critique, eastern philosophy, central asian thinkers, zoroastrianism moral law, spirituality and morality, humanism and moral values wisdom and knowledge integration

Introduction

The 21st century, the beginning of the third millennium, turned out to be not easy for all of

humanity. It brought many progressive changes associated with the rapid development of science and technology, and the emergence of new highly developed technologies. But, at the same time, it was precisely this stage of human society that was faced with rather intractable global problems caused, first of all, by the “separation of culture from its moral foundations,” “excessive material concern,” and a utilitarian-pragmatic understanding of the meaning of human life. As a result, questions arose with renewed vigor about the correctness of the choice of development paths adopted in Western (technogenic) civilization, and, as a consequence, about the adequacy of its ideological orientations and ideals. Humanity was faced with the problem of choosing new survival strategies and began to look for them in the ideas developed in traditional Eastern teachings. Since it was in Eastern philosophy, and in the most concentrated form in the teachings of thinkers of Central Asia, that the tradition of the priority of spiritual values was especially clearly formed.

Spirituality is always associated with a person going beyond selfish interests and primitive needs. It proceeds from the fact that the goals and vital interests of the individual are rooted in a system of over individual values. In true spirituality, in all its manifestations, morality always dominates. Thinkers of Central Asia have always focused their attention on this.

The analysis of the concept of man, the moral improvement of the individual, in our opinion, from its origins, namely from the moral values of Zoroastrianism. Since in the culture of the nations and peoples living on the territory of Central Asia, since ancient times, a special place was occupied by the moral law of Zoroastrianism - the unity of a good thought, a good word and a good deed. That is, a person's spiritual perfection here was assessed not only by good thoughts and words, but also by good deeds.

Literature review

In the history of the development of social thought, the moral perception of the surrounding world was most clearly manifested later in the works of our great compatriots Farabi, Ibn Sina, Biruni, Alisher Navoi, and other thinkers. They saw the goal of moral life in the continuous struggle between virtue and vice, good and evil. The moral ideals of humanity - “goodness”, “dignity”, “love”, “justice”, etc., reflecting higher order values are reflected in their concepts of moral improvement of the individual.

The word “kamal” or “kamalun” translated from Arabic means “perfection”, “full”; “al-insan al-kamil” – means “morally perfect person”, “virtuous person”. Farabi and Ibn Sina pursued the idea of “kamalun” as the main principle of building a virtuous city. According to Farabi's

teachings, evil is the fruit of irrationality, and the only way to acquire sanity is enlightenment. Good is a value in the name of which the most noble deeds and deeds are performed.¹ [1. P.138]

What is the essence of good and its significance for man and society was considered by our great predecessors in their teaching “al-insan al-kamil”. Farabi connects the problem of “kamal” precisely with the acquisition of wisdom and knowledge. The highest wisdom for Farabi is to be virtuous, therefore a perfect person according to Farabi is a virtuous person. He understands good as the unity of knowledge and activity, therefore knowledge of good cannot remain in the form of contemplation, it must be realized in moral action. At the same time, improvement is an eternal process of development of a person who loves wisdom. The question of perfection begins with the acquisition of wisdom and ends with an understanding of moral improvement as the meaning of one’s life. In his “Treatise on the views of the inhabitants of a virtuous city,” he wrote that a person who has achieved perfection must have a discerning mind, as well as “love the truth and its champions, hate lies and those who resort to it; have a proud soul and value honor, his soul must be above base deeds and by nature strive for sublime deeds; despise dirhams, dinars and other attributes of worldly life, love by nature justice and its champions, hate injustice and tyranny and those from whom they come; to be fair, but not stubborn, not to be willful and not to persist in the face of justice². ” [2. P. _ 221.]

Being encyclopedist scientists, our great compatriots put forward the idea of “the integrity of the world”, the harmony of man and society. Universal harmony, in their opinion, is achieved not only by wisdom, deep insight into the essence of things, awareness of the meaning of human existence, but also by his good deeds and deeds: “the happiness of the soul lies in the improvement of its substance, and the latter is achieved by knowledge and beneficence³.” [3. P. _ 332.] Based on the idea of social determinism, the interconnection and interdependence of people’s lives in society, our great compatriots have repeatedly expressed the idea that the good of an individual is connected with the good of others, and that in society a person cannot live only for his well-being, since the interests people are interconnected. This is exactly what Alisher Navoi meant when he wrote in his “Five”: “If you made it your banner to benefit people, then this benefit will be yours”

¹See: Abu Nasr Forobii. Fazilat, bakht-saodat va kamolot khaqida. - T., 2002; See also: Abu Nasr Forobii. Fozil odamlar shahri. - T., 1993 (in Uzbek).

²Al-Farabi. Selected treatises. Almaty. 1994. -P.221.

³Ibn Sina. Selected philosophical works. – M., 1980.-S. 332.

The outstanding scientist Abu Raykhon Beruni believed that “...desire is achieved by applying labor, and obtaining good is by spending something expensive⁴. ” [4. P.9 . _] Developing this idea, he wrote: “Kindness consists in the desire for good to all people in general, and relatives in particular, in case of powerlessness - with a good wish, and, if possible, with deeds... As for the appearance of the soul in (the sense of) morality and way of life, then a man who has control over his passions has the power to change it, turning its negative aspects into praiseworthy ones, as he is persuaded to educate his soul, treat it with spiritual healing and gradually remove its ailments in the ways indicated in the books on morality⁵. ” [5. P.21 . _]

Conceptual ideas of humanism and morality found their expression in the works of Ibn Sina. Thus, wisdom, according to Ibn Sina, is the basis and source not only of obtaining human knowledge, but also of moral relations between people. For man is endowed with such power through which he is able to separate good from evil, perfection from baseness, intellectual maturity from error and lies.⁶ [6. P.45 . _] Man as a rational being occupies a special place in nature. Thanks to reason, he becomes a person free from the dominant influence of random and elemental forces of nature and subordinating his activities to the requirements of the “scales of wisdom.”

Relationships between people are built on the principles of virtue and nobility. Ibn Sina wrote: “wishing to benefit another person, we wish to acquire a good name or hope for reward, or we act as we should in order to show good will and fulfill our duty, since fulfilling a duty for us is a moral dignity, merit and virtue. If we do not do this, we will not acquire these commendable qualities, nor virtue, nor nobility.”⁷ [7. P.141 . _]

He notes that the mind “sees that from which goodness, order and happiness flow.” When a person is completely freed from his moral vices and bad habits that humiliate him as a person, he “learns without unnecessary difficulties and burdens, and becomes useful and pleasant to others.”⁸ [8. P.47 . _] Ideas about the moral improvement of the individual are clearly reflected in Ibn Sina’s philosophical work “Indications and Instructions.” These ideas are presented in a unique allegorical form in his works of art - “Hay ibn Yakzon”, “Risolatut Tair”, “Salomon and

⁴Abu Rayhan Beruni. Selected works. T.V. __ Collection of information for knowledge of jewelry (Mineralogy). M., 1963. –P.9.

⁵Right there. –P.21.

⁶Nasyrov R. On the problem of the unity of knowledge and morality based on the work of Ibn Sina “Tadbiri manzil” // Social sciences in Uzbekistan. – Tashkent, 1991.- No. 8.- P.45.

⁷Ibn Sina. Selected philosophical works. – M., 1980. - P.141.

⁸Nasyrov R. On the problem of the unity of knowledge and morality based on the work of Ibn Sina “Tadbiri manzil” // Social sciences in Uzbekistan. – Tashkent, 1991.- No. 8. – P.47.

Ibsol” and “Kissatu Yusuf”. In them, the thinker talks about the world and man, about the meaning of life; through artistic images and symbols he expresses his moral ideas about good and evil, about the wisdom and destructiveness of vicious desires. They reflect the rich life experience of a scientist and thinker.

A unique concept of moral improvement of man (“al-insan al-kamil”) was developed by Alisher Navoi. His concept is based on the idea of a person’s continuous struggle with vicious inclinations, in overcoming the passions of the soul. These ideas were reflected in the teaching of tasawwuf, which arose in Central Asia in the 11th-12th centuries . and had a great influence on the work of many outstanding poets and thinkers, such as Saadi Sherazi, Alisher Navoi. So in his poem “The Confusion of the Righteous” Navoi wrote:

“You can’t call a trader a Sufi,
At least you won’t find any physical discord in them.
I’m not talking about the physical soul,
I look at the highest degree of spirit.
There’s a difference between heart and soul
They are sometimes confused by name.
The soul above the rose of mystery is a nightingale,
A lamp in the home of sincere people...
The shrine of the Kaaba attracts hearts;
The soul is the shrine of the eternal creator.
But the soul must go through a difficult path,
To find the treasury.”⁹[9. P.45-46 . _]

The concept of man, the problem of moral improvement of the individual, also found its philosophical understanding in Navoi’s work “Mahbub ul-kulub” (“Beloved of Hearts”), written by him shortly before his death in 1500. The work consists of three parts. The first part gives a moral and psychological description of people of various classes and professions, talks about their advantages and disadvantages, about just and unjust rulers, about court dignitaries and their morals, etc. In the second part of the book, the author examines moral virtues, their place and role in the life of society. Here Navoi gives a philosophical and ethical analysis and defines the criteria for a person’s moral life. The final third part contains aphorisms, catchphrases and deep wise sayings.

⁹Alisher Navoi. Poems. Translation from Old Uzbek. Moscow: Fiction. 1972. –pp.45-46.

In them, the poet and thinker promotes the idea that only a highly spiritual person combines moral and intellectual strength, and this is the main weapon that elevates him above all other living beings. As M. Aripov rightly notes in his study dedicated to the work of Alisher Navoi, his “ deep thoughts about man and his spiritual world, reflections on the universe and the meaning of life are viewed through the prism of the concepts of “love” and “beauty.” Love is a spiritualized moral force that cleanses a person from the scum of passions and prophets, educates him in the spirit of high moral principles, instructs him on the path of nobility, courage of spirit and tests of fidelity, requiring the active manifestation by a person of his abilities and spiritual powers. Such love requires self-improvement and self-knowledge from a person, dooms him to a lot of torment and suffering ¹⁰.” [10. P.26 . _]

When discussing the concept of moral improvement of the individual, it is important to highlight another extremely important aspect in the teachings of Central Asian thinkers, which resonates with the modern search for new values and strategies for human life. We are talking about the relationship between morality and truth. So Ibn Sina wrote: “What is good for the mind is, according to one opinion, the truth, and according to another, it is a benefit¹¹. ” [eleven. P.310]. Beruni believed that the sciences “gave rise to human needs necessary for his life ¹². ” [12. P.84-87 . _] In his famous work “India” he wrote: “There are many areas of knowledge, and they become even more numerous when the minds of people of the era of ascending development turn to them in a continuous sequence; a sign of the latter is people’s desire for science, their respect for them and their representatives ¹³. ” [13. P.438 . _] However, in order for the truth to be revealed to a person, he needs moral self-education. A person’s activity aimed at comprehending the external world and his activity aimed at improving his own inner world must be coordinated and presuppose each other.

Thus, an analysis of the concept of moral improvement of the individual, thinkers of Central Asia, allows us to identify their following fundamental principles:

– philanthropy, i.e. the principle of humanism, which actively forms the ideal of a person and answers the question of the meaning of life, based on the understanding of a person not as a means, but as an end;

¹⁰ Aripov M. Humanism of Alisher Navoi. –T.1991. –P.26.

¹¹ Ibn Sina. Selected philosophical works - P. 310.

¹² Abu Rayhan Beruni. Selected works. T. III . Determining the boundaries of places to clarify the distances between settlements (Geodesy). M., 1966. -WITH. 84-87.

¹³ Abu Rayhan Beruni. Selected works. T. II . India. M., 1963.–P.438.

- relative autonomy of a person and independence in relation to the world as a whole, manifested in freedom of choice, life position;
- reason, knowledge as the basis for achieving moral improvement;
- morality, as the highest spiritual value, revealing the content of such concepts as “goodness”, “love”, “courage”, “justice”, “responsibility”, “happiness”, “honesty”, “dignity”, “duty”, which make a person strong, direct him to positive deeds;
- human life activity as the main criterion of his moral perfection;
- the need for self-education, i.e. spiritual self-improvement of the individual, which is expressed in the process of a person’s continuous struggle with vicious inclinations, in overcoming the “passions of the soul”;
- moral improvement of the individual, as the main condition for the formation of a virtuous society and state, the achievement of universal harmony.

The ideas put forward by outstanding medieval thinkers and scientists of Central Asia within the framework of the concept of moral improvement of the individual are also relevant in the modern world. Since the problems that modern civilization faces are fundamentally related, first of all, to the loss of the moral core of spiritual culture, the dominant position of material well-being in the scale of civilization values.

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